

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

Check it out ECS profiles on the EdiCitNet toolbox web.

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

WP2 is very glad to announce that the ECS profile (in English) is already available on the EdiCitNet toolbox web.

The ECS PROFILE aims to promote an interactive and inclusive knowledge sharing among people already involved, or willing to get involved, with the edible city movement.

The ECS PROFILE showcase diverse information such as:

- Short description
- Starting year
- Type of ECS (i.e private garden, local market, community kitchen)
- Location and contact
- Link to social medias
- List of edible goods and activities
- Network
- Type of ownership and funding
- Marketing strategies
- Initial budget and running cost
- Type of access (private or public)
- Edible and non-edible nature-based solutions
- Production methods

Furthermore, participants of a certain ECS can give their feedback through the ECS profile by clicking on "SHARE YOUR EXPERIENCE".

Additionally, the ECS profile puts forward a unique performance assessment in terms of sustainability, urban challenges and ecosystem services addressed.

Coming soon (spoiler alert)! Currently, WP2 team is working on a set of interactive features which are based on existing social medias such as Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn. The idea is that users will be able to interact with a ECS by leaving comments and questions and following an ECS PROFILE to get updates on events and news.

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

6e309656-ac2f-40ac-912e-08b22477b949/ecs_profile_news.PNG

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

26571f1b-1139-4f51-b8ac-814cb4a44e9e/ecs_profile_assessment.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

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Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

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Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
- No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
- No, none of them
- Only on Twitter
- Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

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